

RESOLUTE
Research Empowerment on Solute Carriers

Project number 777372

**WP3 – Development of
 quantitative transport assays**

D3.2 Assays for SLCs based on fluorescent sensor proteins

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Publishable Summary

The goal of WP3 is the development of quantitative transporter assays for the majority of SLCs. Therefore, we are validating a diverse and wide array of methods for transporter assays. In WP3, we implemented a workflow (Month 24) which starts with reagent availability from WP1 and takes into consideration data from WP2 on deorphanization and cellular localization together with publicly available data mined in WP8. Once the reagents are available for a given SLC, the transport reaction is analysed by the partners in WP3 and a parsimonious preselection of suitable assay methods is performed. Then, the cellular localization is examined and assay development typically proceeds directly if the SLC is expressed at the plasma membrane. For SLC expressed in subcellular compartments, the technology experts assess case-by-case, for instance SLC redirection to the plasma membrane, permeabilizations, cell fractionation or biosensors.

Deliverable D3.2 summarizes our results and protocols for biosensor-based SLC assays. Genetically-encoded biosensors typically consist of one or more fluorescent proteins whose intensities are changed directly upon analyte-binding or indirectly by its binding to a fused analyte-binding-protein. Among the methods within WP3, biosensors stand out, as they are very specific for one analyte and therefore lack general applicability but hold exciting promise since they measure very directly and in a time-resolved manner. Importantly, they also have the unique capability to measure subcellular transport reactions after genetic targeting to cellular compartments. Therefore, biosensors could be very useful in cell-based assay development for SLCs expressed in cellular compartments. Here, we describe the successful assay development for six transporters using three different biosensors and two measurement technologies.

Methods

Biosensors for Chloride and pH: Superclomeleon and pHAxensor (AXXAM)

Over the past decades, many researchers have made major contributions towards the development of Genetically Encoded (GE) fluorescent sensors derived from fluorescent proteins, which have the ability to undergo detectable changes in fluorescence in response to corresponding cell events. GE fluorescent sensors may be used to probe intracellular changes in the concentration of specific ions or variations of pH.

Among them, is the **SuperClomeleon sensor**. SuperClomeleon is a Cl⁻ sensitive ratiometric FRET (Fluorescence Resonance Energy Transfer) sensor obtained by fusing a YFP mutant (Yellow Fluorescent Protein, that is a yellow variant of the GFP with a high sensitivity towards halides) and the Cyan Fluorescent Protein (CFP, insensitive to halides). Intracellular increase of Cl⁻ finally leads to a decrease of the FRET ratio YFP/CFP. The figure below (Figure 1) shows the Superclomeleon assay principle and the excitation/emission wavelengths:

Figure 1: Assay principle for Superclomeleon sensor.

Other important GE fluorescent sensors are **pHluorins**, which are pH-sensitive variants of green fluorescent protein, that allow measurement of intracellular pH in living cells. At acidic pH, pHluorin is quenched, whereas at physiological pH, pHluorin fluorescence increases. AXXAM has developed a proprietary AXXAM pH sensor (**pHAxensor**) which is a chimera between a Red Fluorescent Protein (RFP) (which is the portion of the sensor insensitive to pH) and a pH-sensitive Green fluorescent protein (whose fluorescence is quenched at acidic pH). The pHAxensor shows a high dynamic range for pH measurement in living cells and pKa around 7; in addition, the pH sensitivity in a full linear range is comprised between 6.4-7.7, as shown in the figure below (Figure 2):

Figure 2: Features of the pHAxensor.

When the assay validation was carried out using the GE biosensors, a transient transfection step into the HEK-293 JumpIn T-REx cell line Over-Expressing (OE) the SLC under investigation, had to be carried out. Typically, OE cell lines were seeded in 384-well plate format and then transiently transfected the day after with the biosensor expressing construct. The cell line, expressing both the biosensor and the target SLC, was typically tested 48h after the transfection. Typically, medium was manually discarded and cells were washed and incubated with the most proper assay buffer (for example, in the case of Superclomeleon, a washing step in Chloride free buffer had to be carried out) before injection of the substrates. For testing GE fluorescent sensors, a fluorescent reader that is able

both to excite the sensor and to acquire fluorescence at proper wavelengths is needed. The use of plate readers such as FLIPR^{TETRA} or Hamamatsu FDSS, that can accommodate 384-well plates format, ensures the high throughput of the assay. For the SuperClomeleon, the CFP was excited (typically at 436 nm), then the emission of both CFP (480 nm) and YFP (535 nm) was acquired by the Hamamatsu FDSS instrument. For the pHAxensor, either the single read mode (in which only the green fluorescence was recorded) or the dual read mode (in which both the green fluorescence as well as the red fluorescence were recorded) were used at our FLIPR^{TETRA} reader.

Biosensor for glucose: FLII12Pglu-700 μ δ 6 (MPIMR)

The FLII12Pglu-700 μ δ 6 biosensor (Takanaga et al. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) – Biomembranes* 2008, p1091) and historically is one of the earliest (Fehr et al. *Mol. Cell. Biol.* 2005, p11102) and more widely used (cited 171 times) metabolite biosensors. Therefore, we chose this biosensor to highlight the usefulness and practicality of biosensors in transporter-assays. It is a fusion of the *E. Coli* glucose/galactose-binding protein MglB with ECFP and Citrine-YFP. An increase in glucose concentration (dynamic range 0.05 – 11 mM) results in an increased FRET efficiency that can be observed by an increase in Citrine acceptor emission and a decrease in ECFP donor emission.

HEK293 JumpIN TRex cell lines were cultured in high-glucose DMEM supplemented with 10% dialyzed FBS at 37 °C in a humidified incubator at 5% CO₂. Cells were subcultured three times per week or at ~90% confluency using Trypsin-EDTA and were regularly tested for mycoplasma infection. Two days prior to the assay, cells were split to 30-50% confluency in two T75 flasks. To one flask 1 ug/mL doxycycline was added after 4-6h to allow for cell attachment. The following day, doxycycline was removed and cells were transfected with 10 ug / T75 FLII12Pglu-700 μ δ 6 using Lipofectamine 2000 or 3000 according to the manufacturer's instructions. After one day, cells were starved for 2h in 10% dial. FBS/no-glucose DMEM. Then, cells were trypsinized, collected by centrifugation, resuspended in 5 mL / T75 10% dial. FBS/PBS, filtered through a cell strainer and diluted to a total volume of 18 mL / T75. 96w U-bottom plates were prepared containing 40 uL of a 5X stock containing glucose and test compounds. 160 ul of cell suspension was then added and incubated for 3-5 minutes before transferral to the LSR II Fortessa flow cytometer (BD Biosciences) HTS module. Doxycycline-induced cells and non-induced cells were always measured on the same 96 well plate. Cells were gated for expression in the FITC channel (Ex 488nm / Em 530/30), measured for FRET donor emission in the BV421 channel (Ex 405 nm / Em 450/50) and for FRET acceptor emission in the BV510 channel (Ex 405 nm / Em 525/50). Analysis was performed with FlowJo10 software, cells were gated for live singlets (SSC-A vs FSC-A) and sensor expression (FITC positive). The FRET intensity ratio was derived by dividing the BV510 by the BV421 channel and was used for subsequent analysis, which is represented as mean FRET/CFP \pm 95% CI.

Results

Biosensors for Chloride and pH: Superclomelon and pHAxensor (AXXAM)

A significant reduction (~80%) of the FRET ratio was observed in the SLC12A3 doxy-induced condition upon injection of 65 mM Cl⁻ (**Fig. 3**). A reduction of FRET ratio (~60%) was also detected in the SLC12A3 not induced condition (data not shown) due to the leakage of the system. In both WT doxy-induced (data reported in the graph) and not-induced (data not shown) conditions, the observed reduction of FRET ratio was similar (~30%) and was most likely due to the passive diffusion of Cl⁻ ions within the cells. This reduction was significantly lower than the reduction observed in the SLC12A3 doxy-induced condition.

Figure 3: Assay results for SLC12A3 with Superclomelon. Left panel: Time-course of CFP and YFP(FRET) fluorescence intensity after injection of 65 mM Cl⁻. **Right panel:** The reduction in FRET ratio of cells overexpressing SLC12A3 is larger than in wild-type cells.

In all experiments with pHXsensor and SLC16A3/MCT4, before injection of the substrate, cells were incubated with AZD3965 (a specific inhibitor of MCT-1 and MCT-2, that are endogenously expressed in the HEK-293 cell line) at a concentration of 100 nM (30 min incubation, **Fig. 4**) to reduce background transport. Then, lactate was injected in buffer supplemented with HCl to reach a final pH of 6.8. In the presence of protons, the two doses of lactate induced a higher quenching of the green fluorescent signal in the SLC16A3-induced condition. Both the red and green fluorescence recordings are shown (**Fig. 4 lower panels**). The red fluorescence was unchanged due to the pH-insensitivity of this portion of the biosensor. In contrast, the green reporter fluorescence (pH sensitive) is quenched upon transporter activation (**Fig. 4 right panels**). The green fluorescence change in SLC16A3-induced cells was significantly larger than in not-induced cells (**Fig. 4 upper panels**).

Green fluorescence recordings (single read mode)

Figure 4: Assay results for SLC16A3 with pHXsensor. Upper panels: SLC16A3-induced cells show a larger response than not induced cells. **Lower panels:** Dual-read mode showing that only the

reporter-Fluorescence is changing upon substrate injection but not the red fluorescence used for normalization.

Biosensor for glucose: FLII12Pglu-700 $\mu\delta$ 6 (MPIMR)

For all tested glucose transporters SLC2A1-4/GLUT1-4, a difference could be observed in glucose transport in induced vs non-induced cells (**Fig. 5**). In general, the $K_{0.5}$ for glucose in induced cells was shifted to lower values due to the overexpression of the transporter. In addition, the resting glucose concentration is higher in induced cells. Three inhibitors (BAY-876, Cytochalasin B, WZB117) with different selectivity profiles were tested on all cell lines in presence of 1 mM glucose. At this glucose concentration, close to no transport was observed in non-induced cells (**Fig. 5 a-d upper left panels**) offering a large assay window specific for the induced-transporter. The determined IC_{50} values for induced cells is shifted to higher values compared to non-induced cells. This is expected due to the higher, induced expression level of the transporters. In comparison to literature values (**Table 1**), the experimental values are considerably higher, again likely due to the very high transporter expression levels in the HEK293 JumpIN TRex cell system. In addition, the biosensor assay measures glucose directly and might be saturated at lower concentration, whereas classical methods rely on cell lysates and coupled enzymatic reactions to produce a luminescent readout. The known selectivity profiles were fully confirmed for all tested inhibitors, *i.e.* Bay-879 blocking GLUT1>GLUT4>>GLUT2/3; Cytochalasin B blocking GLUT1/3/4>GLUT2 and WZB117 blocking GLUT4>GLUT2>GLUT1/3.

Figure 5: Assay results for a) SLC2A1 b) SLC2A2 c) SLC2A3 c) SLC2A4. Green: doxycycline-

induced cells; Red: non-induced.

Table 1: Summary of experimental IC₅₀ values and comparison to literature values ([1] Siebeneicher et al. *ChemMedChem* **2016**, 11(20), 2261. [2] Ojelabi et al. *Journal of Biological Chemistry* **2016**, 291(52), 26762-26772.)

	BAY-876						Cytochalasin B					WZB 117	
	Literature IC ₅₀ (uM) [1]	Selectivity	Experimental IC ₅₀ (uM)	Selectivity			Literature IC ₅₀ (uM) [1]	Selectivity	Experimental IC ₅₀ (uM)	Selectivity		Literature IC ₅₀ (uM) [2]	Experimental IC ₅₀ (uM)
SLC2A1	0.002	1	0.23	1		SLC2A1	0.1	1	4.1	1		10	> 50
SLC2A2	10.8	5400	> 10	> 44		SLC2A2	2.8	28	40	10			32
SLC2A3	1.67	835	> 10	> 44		SLC2A3	0.12	1	3.9	1		10	> 25
SLC2A4	0.29	145	5.5	24		SLC2A4	0.28	3	3.9	1		0.2	2.5

Table 2: Reagents and Resources

Reagents and Resources	Source	Identifier
Cell lines		
HEK293 JumpIN TRex SLC2A1 WT-OE	RESOLUTE	#CE02C3-F
HEK293 JumpIN TRex SLC2A2 WT-OE	RESOLUTE	#CE02B8-R
HEK293 JumpIN TRex SLC2A3 WT-OE	RESOLUTE	#CE02BP-2
HEK293 JumpIN TRex SLC2A4 WT-OE	RESOLUTE	#CE02C4-S
HEK293 JumpIN TRex SLC12A1 WT-OE	RESOLUTE	#CE024G-H
HEK293 JumpIN TRex SLC12A3 WT-OE	RESOLUTE	#CE025B-M
HEK293 JumpIN TRex SLC16A3 WT-OE	RESOLUTE	#CE00TF-K
Chemicals		
Cytochalasin B	Alfa Aesar	#J65342
WZB117	Selleckchem	#S7927
BAY-876	Selleckchem	#S8452

Doxycycline hyclate	Alfa Aesar	#J60579
Glucose solution	Gibco	#A2494001
Cell culture reagents		
DMEM, high glucose, GlutaMAX™ Supplement, pyruvate	Gibco	#10569010
DMEM, no Glucose	Gibco	#11966025
Sodium pyruvate 100X	Gibco	#11360070
OptiMEM	Gibco	#31985070
PBS	Gibco	#10010023
Trypsin-EDTA 0.05%	Gibco	#25300054
FBS Qualified, HI	Gibco	#10500-064
Dialyzed FBS	Gibco	#A3382001
Lipofectamine 2000	Thermo-Fisher	#11668027
Lipofectamine 3000	Thermo-Fisher	#L3000008
Plasmids		
FLII12Pglu-700μδ6	Addgene	#17866
Superclomeleon	Sequence reported in Grimley et al., J Neurosci. 2013, page 3	Sequence reported in Grimley et al., J Neurosci. 2013, page 3
pHAXsensor	proprietary	proprietary
Instruments		
LSR II Fortessa flow cytometer with HTS module	BD Biosciences	
Hamamatsu FDSS	Hamamatsu	

FLIPR ^{TETRA}	Molecular Devices	
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Conclusion

In conclusion, in WP3 we succeeded in the validation three biosensors (for chloride, pH and glucose) in cell-based assays while employing two measurement technologies (plate-reader and flow cytometer). This led to successful development of a total number of six assays (**Table 3**). In one case, for SLC12A1, no chloride transport could be measured and assay development failed. This transporter will be addressed using an alternative detection method. Overall, biosensors proved to be a highly successful and valuable method in WP3, with an overall success rate of 6 out of 7 assays.

No deviations from the original plan.

Table 3: Summary of assay development

Contributor	SLC	Alias	Read-out	Substrate	Outcome
AXXAM	SLC12A1		Superclomeleon	Na ⁺ /K ⁺ /Cl ⁻ co-transporter	NOT VALIDATED
AXXAM	SLC12A3	NCC	Superclomeleon	Na ⁺ /Cl ⁻ co-transporter	VALIDATED
AXXAM	SLC16A3	MCT4	pH encoded biosensor	Lactate, H ⁺	VALIDATED
MPIMR	SLC2A1	GLUT1	Glucose biosensor	glucose	VALIDATED
MPIMR	SLC2A2	GLUT2	Glucose biosensor	glucose	VALIDATED
MPIMR	SLC2A3	GLUT3	Glucose biosensor	glucose	VALIDATED
MPIMR	SLC2A4	GLUT4	Glucose biosensor	glucose	VALIDATED

Repository for primary data

Primary data are stored in the ReSolute SharePoint in the WP3 folder. As part of the data management plan, we are currently evaluating systematic and sustainable publication procedures for assay protocols and characteristics in public databases like PubChem.